

Psychological Preparation of Football Players during the Competition

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Abstract:

Psychological training of football players, solving important problems - improving the ability to manage their emotional state. Teaching to control one's own mental state, not only during the competition, but also during the training, leading 11 people in the cycle during the year.

Keywords: Sport, athlete, competition, preparation, opponent, victory, defeat, draw, reward.

INTRODUCTION.

Decree PF 5368 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated March 5, 2018 "On measures to radically improve the state management system in the field of physical education and sports" and Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated March 16, 2018 "On measures to further develop football" - Decision 3610 created great opportunities for the field of physical education and sports of our country, including football officials of our country. In accordance with the implementation of these decisions and decrees, promising changes are being made in the sport of our country, especially football.

As the tasks of developing sports in our country and strengthening its position on the world scale are defined at the level of state policy, the issues of raising training and effectiveness of each sport to new levels are required to be urgently resolved. In particular, paying special attention to the sport of football puts responsible tasks before specialists.

MAIN PART.

Psychological preparation for the competition begins from the moment of knowing that the athlete will participate in this competition. The main task of psychological preparation for the competition

is to create a state of readiness for the game in the player, and this state must be maintained during the game. The state of preparation is expressed as the mental state of the athlete as follows:

- ✓ self-confidence;
- ✓ strive to fight to the end and win;
- ✓ sufficient stability of the emotional state;
- ✓ being able to control one's behavior, mood and feelings;
- ✓ the ability to mobilize all forces to achieve the goal.

The psychological preparation of a football player in the pre-competition period consists of the following sections or components:

1. Collecting the necessary and reliable information about the opponents and the conditions of the upcoming competition.
2. Before the start of the competition, fill in information about the athlete's capabilities, training status, and if necessary, change them.
3. Correct determination of the purpose of participation in the competition.
4. Approximate programming of the competition process, modeling the conditions of the future competition and the probability of determining the direction of the tactical plan, that is, choosing the optimal option of the approximate program corresponding to the conditions of the future competition.
5. Special preparation for encountering different levels of difficulties encountered in the competition (especially sudden ones) and carrying out special exercises to overcome them.
6. Prediction of the methods of self-management in internal negative situations and external environmental conditions that may occur.
7. Knowing how to choose and use methods to keep the nervous and mental state fresh before the competition and to be able to restore oneself during the competition.

"Modeling" of the competition conditions is an important means of psychological preparation before the competition. To model the game, the coach first carefully analyzes the conditions of the upcoming competition, especially the opponents, the external environment (temperature, the reaction of the spectators, the venue of the competition, etc.).

In order to keep the player's nerves in the pre-competition period, it is necessary to set such an agenda for him that, on the one hand, he strictly adheres to the requirements of the sports regime, and on the other hand, it is necessary to include interesting and distracting activities in the regime. For example: group walks, watching comedy movies, listening to your favorite music, going out of town, etc. It is necessary to take into account the individual passion and taste of the players.

An important problem of psychological training of a football player is to improve his ability to manage his emotional state. Learning how to manage your own mental state should be carried out not only during the preparation of 11 people for the competition, but also during the training cycle during the year. Therefore, the coach must explain in depth that the methods of self-discipline and management are of great importance in overcoming in order to prepare them in each training session, and it is necessary to systematically ask the athletes to improve these methods.

Psychological preparation for the upcoming game. There is no need to think about the game when the players are prepared for the match by identifying the opponent's actions for the match and preparing them before the match. There may be other options for preparing for the game.

The main task of the coach who prepares the players for the upcoming match is to reduce the excessive nervousness that occurs in the players before going to the difficult field, to create a combative state of self-confidence in them. That being said, don't let your faith in athletes turn into overconfidence.

Because this composure leads to loss of vigilance and reduced concentration. There are a number of methods in the psychological practice of preparing an athlete for competition. The coach can use them selectively. Not only the coach, but also the athlete should prepare himself for the upcoming meeting. For this, he should learn to use the following methods before the meeting. These include: self-influence, self-persuasion, self-encouragement, self-command, etc. Autogenic training before a game can help dramatically, especially for overexcited, unbalanced players.

The analysis during the study also showed that there are shortcomings in the team's training aimed at planning preparation. In this regard, one of the important factors is to make clarifications in the planning of the training process, develop training programs and work plans aimed at training football players, taking into account the characteristics of the girls' body, developing control standards aimed at studying the levels of training, or necessarily using existing, scientifically based standards in practice in the training process. is considered

Psychological preparation of the team during the rest period between sections. Correct advice of the coach plays an important role in the psychological preparation of the players during the match. It should be noted that if the coach cannot control himself and the negative situations before the start, he should refrain from giving advice, because his negative situation will quickly transfer to his players. In order to mobilize the player's will to one or another action, it is possible to influence his character traits, personality, or to use important motives specific to the team in his participation in the competition.

The experience of working with athletes in competitions of various scales has shown that if the athlete's mind is focused on the result, without emphasizing the means of achieving the goal, an obstacle is created in achieving the goal.

It is necessary to apply various methods that affect the athlete's behavior and psyche carefully and adapt to them. If the game is going according to plan and there is no need to change the game, then there is no need to advise.

In conclusion, it should be said that the development of football in our country means that the training process should be improved. Every factor that affects the effective organization of the process must be taken into account, it should be developed and implemented on the basis of appropriate regulatory documents, planning the distribution of hours in the planning of training types in accordance with the stages of long-term training, etc. remains one of the issues awaiting solution.

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